
MENTORING STRATEGIES AND SECONDARY SCHOOL EFFECTIVENESS IN ILORIN EAST KWARA STATE: A SYMBIOTIC EXAMINATION

Olubukola James Ojo^{1*}, Joseph Ojische Ogar², Adedapo Adetiba A. Atolagbe¹,
Eniola Keji Ola-Alani¹

University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria¹

University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria²

*Email: ojo.oj@unilorin.edu.ng

Received: December 2022

Accepted: January 2023

Published: June 2023

ABSTRACT

Education is a necessary tool for national development and for development to take place, it is important that teachers who are the driving force of passing instructions to students in the school must be properly mentored for them to carry out their assignments. It is on the basis of this background that this study was conducted. Descriptive survey research design was found suitable for the study. A multistage sampling technique was employed in this research and 100 respondents were selected for the study. Four research questions and hypotheses were raised and formulated and a questionnaire titled mentoring strategies and school effectiveness was developed for data gathering. The instrument was validated and the reliability coefficient of .84 was achieved. The finding revealed that there was significant relationship between mentoring strategies and secondary school effectiveness in Ilorin East, Kwara State. It was recommended among other things that teachers should be trained using mentoring strategies and that school administrators should ensure activities which will involve pairing new with experienced teachers so that they will gain new experience from the models.

Keywords: mentoring strategies, secondary school effectiveness, modelling, teamwork and effective communication

UJER

Suggested citation:

Ojo, O. J., Ogar, J. O., Atolagbe, A. A., & Ola-Alani, E. K. (2023). Mentoring Strategies and Secondary School Effectiveness in Ilorin East Kwara State: A Symbiotic Examination. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 2(2), 78-85.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the bedrock for national development. It is the process of acquiring and developing competences, skills and abilities that is necessary for the growth and progress of any nation. It is not surprising, therefore, that it lies at the heart of every society who is desirous of development. The educational institution as a formal organization is characterized by a lot of actors. Actors such as the school heads, teachers, non-teachers and students are found in a school system. The school head is the chief executive officer of the school he/she is saddled with the responsibilities of ensuring that appropriate guidance is provided for all the other actors in the school. As a school head, the task of the school cannot be single-handedly carried out by him/her alone; since this is true, he/she has to mentor those under his care for quality and effective execution of all the school tasks. A mentor is an individual with many years of experience who is saddled with the responsibility of giving support, insightful advice and guidance to inexperienced teachers for quality delivery of activities which could result into effectiveness of tasks. When mentoring is properly undertaken in schools, quality can be achieved in the teaching and learning process. High quality professional development can be ensured only through commitment, devotion and dedication of teachers, who are supported by mentors.

Mentoring process is a symbiotic endeavor because it involves a relationship between a mentor and a mentee. It is a partnership and relationship between two people (mentor and mentee). The importance of mentoring strategies on secondary school effectiveness cannot be over emphasized. It must be noted that for a school to be regarded as being effective, it must possess some characteristics which differs it from other school in terms of achievement. Hence, the combination of a set of strategies would foster the effectiveness of a school. Secondary school effectiveness can be achieved when mentoring programme is put in place.

Merrick (2007) sees mentoring as a situation whereby an individual such as a teacher, coach or an employer willingly invests time in the development of another in a trusting relationship. It is conceived as a two-way process where a mentor provides advice, shares knowledge and experiences for the mentees to improve their performance on the job. Mentoring is an assistance given to an employee in order to enable him grow and develop in the profession and improve on his role performance (Olowu, 2013). A study was conducted by Olu-Ajayi in (2013) on the effect of mentoring on the cognitive achievement of low performing Biology students. It was found that mentoring should be used by teachers as an adjunct to normal classroom teaching for bringing up slow and poor students to improved level of performance. Mentoring contributes to the enhancement of employees' skills and knowledge, which in turn culminate into the overall outcome and performance of staff in their jobs (Koirela & Dhungana, 2015; Roll-Hansen, 2012)

Mentorship according to Ukaegbu, Alex-Nmecha and Horsfall (2014) is the act of training someone for the person to grow. Furthermore, mentoring can be considered as a powerful tool of empowering mentees. It is considered as a learning process aimed at making the mentee to grow. In the words of Klinge (2015), mentoring denotes an individual evolving connection with an expert or more experienced individual aiding or guiding non-expert person. Ofobruku and Nwakoby (2015) submitted that a mentor as a person who facilitates personal and professional growth of an individual or employee by sharing the knowledge and insight that have been learned through for a long period of time. Kumar, Singh and Kumar (2017) submitted that mentoring is an on-the-job training framework to enhance superior skills, knowledge, capabilities and outlook of the employees that results in effective performance of the workers and attainment of organizational goals. It involves a junior or beginner teachers being placed under the mentorship and supervision of a more senior teacher to facilitate his personal and professional growth (Undiyaundeye & Basake, 2017).

Peretomode and Pkoya (2019) summarized mentoring as a combination of emotional and practical support geared towards guiding staff on specific areas for effective performance. Osemeke (2020) argued that the traditional methods of developing staff are becoming too expensive and time consuming, and that greater number of employers is now devising more creative and effective means of achieving competence

development at optimal cost. According to this researcher, one key staff capacity building tool embraced by many organizations, in addition to formal training and learning is mentoring.

Undiyaundeye and Basake (2017) in their study on mentoring and career development of academics in colleges of education in Cross River State, Nigeria noted that mentoring is associated with risk, change, staff competition, unethical career practices, high uncertainty, unfavourable government policy implementation and ignorance of the role of mentors being in control of the weak site. It was discovered in their study that mentoring relationships exists among academic staff and it is the basis for enhanced performance of lecturers. Akpan, Owhor and Nsikan (2017) focused on workplace mentoring strategies and sustainable commitment of university teaching hospital staff in South-South Region of Nigeria. It was revealed in their study that managers of healthcare personnel to attach more importance/interest to group/team, one-protégé-one mentor, and informal mentoring because it has been found to significantly contribute to overall workers commitment.

A study on the impact of mentoring on nursing and midwifery educators and students was carried out by Ekong and Carolyne (2017). The outcome of their research revealed that mentoring is thought to enhance teachers' competencies, strengthen social abilities, and promote learning and career development. It was found that senior faculty mentoring junior faculty provided or enhanced accomplishments of some nurse educator core competencies, provided opportunities to develop teaching knowledge base, and promoted exposure to required resources for growth in the teaching career. Malik, Agunbiade and Arikewuyo (2019) investigated the effects of peer mentoring strategy on students' performance in mathematics at senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria, the result of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the performance of students involved in peer mentoring strategy and the students involved using traditional strategy.

Odimmega, Udemba and Obiekwe (2021) in their study focused on the strategies for mentoring secondary school new teachers for greater performance in Anambra State. It was found out from their study that the principals rated collaborative curriculum alignment and classroom observation to a high extent in enhancing performance of new business teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State. Another study which investigated mentoring service and in-service training predictors of quality job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State was carried out by Amadi and Abraham (2021). The findings of the study revealed that mentoring had a low, positive and significant relationship with teacher quality job performance while in-service training had high, positive and significant relationship with teacher quality job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Extant literature has revealed the findings of similar studies. However, most of them still differ considerably from the current study. For instance, Undiyaundeye and Basake (2017) looked at mentoring and career development of academics but exclude secondary school effectiveness. Furthermore, Undiyaundeye and Basake (2017) carried out their study in colleges of education in Cross River State, Nigeria but the present study was carried out in Kwara State, Nigeria. Akpan et. al (2017) focused on workplace mentoring strategies and sustainable commitment but left out secondary school effectiveness. Also, Akpan et.al (2017) conducted their study among university teaching hospital staff in South-South region of Nigeria while the present study was conducted in secondary school effectiveness in Kwara State, Nigeria. Ekong and Carolyne (2017) looked at mentoring on nursing and midwifery educators and students but their study did not include effectiveness of secondary schools in their study. Malik et.al (2019) in their study investigated the effects of peer mentoring strategy on students' performance in mathematics at senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria but aspect of school effectiveness was not considered. Odimmega et.al (2021) looked at strategies for mentoring secondary school new teachers for greater performance in Anambra State but left alone the aspect that concerns effectiveness of the schools.

From the array of literature reviewed, it is evident that the roles played by mentoring in the overall success of a school cannot be undermined. Looking at these studies altogether, none of them focused on secondary school effectiveness. Similarly, none of the earlier researchers have been able to examine the relationship between mentoring strategies and secondary school effectiveness which is the focus of the current study. Again, majority of the studies have focused on the use of mentoring strategies in ICT in

colleges of education, university teaching hospital, but none of them has ever focused on mentoring strategies and secondary school effectiveness in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Ineffectiveness has characterized our secondary schools today and one of the factors responsible for this ineffectiveness is lack of mentoring programmes between experienced teachers and the newly recruited teachers. It is sad to say that secondary schools in Kwara state seem to have ignored mentoring in school administration. A lot of factors have been found to account for this ugly state of affairs, one of which is the inability of principals especially in Kwara state to attach the newly recruited teachers to mentors. Majority of the newly recruited teachers are left to find their own way in schools without proper mentoring exercise which will enable them to effectively participate in school development and this causes these teachers to be frustrated and end up not performing well in their teaching role. Even those who are not new teachers are left without mentorship programmes that will help them to update their knowledge on the current practices in the profession as well as improve school effectiveness. It is believed that a combination of mentoring strategies if properly administered by administration could result in an effective school.

To the best of the researchers' knowledge, no research has been carried out on mentoring strategies and secondary school effectiveness in Secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State; this research therefore intended to fill in this space and also exposed the benefits and challenges attached to mentoring.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the mentoring strategies used by teachers for effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State?
2. Is there a significant relationship between modelling and school effectiveness in Ilorin East secondary school?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teamwork and school effectiveness in Ilorin East secondary school?
4. Is there a significant relationship between effective communication and school effectiveness in Ilorin East secondary school?

Research Hypotheses

Four hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between mentoring strategies and school effectiveness.
2. There is no significant relationship between modelling and school effectiveness in Ilorin East secondary school.
3. There is no significant relationship between teamwork and school effectiveness in Ilorin East secondary school.
4. There is no significant relationship between effective communication and school effectiveness in Ilorin East secondary school.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study made use of descriptive survey research design because data collected was used to describe the existing conditions as they exist without any form of manipulation. Folawiyo (2010) explained that it may involve the exploration of an observed phenomena or the description in a precise form of the characteristics of individuals, groups, people or phenomena in education. A survey in education according to Best and Kahr (2013), enabled the researcher to obtain the opinion of a representative sample of a target population so as to be able to draw references about the entire population.

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique(s)

Daramola (2015) defined population as a set of element, people, objects or events in a given research. The total population for this study comprised of all teachers in the selected sample regardless of their qualification and year of experience was 100. Sampling technique is a systematic process employed to select a required proportion of the target population (Daramola, 2010). According to Ministry of Education and Human Capital Development in Kwara State, the total number of secondary school teachers was 3,102. A multistage sampling technique was employed in this research. In the first stage, purposive random technique was used to select 5 schools each from the 50 senior secondary schools in the case study area. In the second stage, proportionate sampling technique was used to select ten percent (10%) of the population in the public secondary schools. This made a total number of selected respondents to 100. This technique was considered appropriate because it was not bias and each respondent was given equal chance of being selected.

Instrumentation

The questionnaire titled mentoring strategies and school effectiveness was developed and used to collect relevant data on the variables of this study i.e mentoring strategies and school effectiveness. The questionnaire contained 2 sections. Section A contained demographic information of the respondents while section B elicited information on mentoring strategies and school effectiveness in Secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State. The items were based on the 4-points Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD).

The questionnaire was given to three experts in the Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin. Their comments, suggestions and recommendations were used to improve the contents of the questionnaire. Reliability is the degree to which the instrument consistently measures what it intends to measure (Olu, 2013). The reliability of the instrument was carried out by using test-retest and the result after analysis was 0.84 which was found reliable for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents' Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Pearson Moment Correlation was used to test all the postulated hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the mentoring strategies used by teachers for effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State?

Table 1: Ranking Order of Mentoring Strategies used by Teachers for Effectiveness

S/N	Statement	N	X	SD	Rank
1	Modelling	100	1.52	.70	2 nd
2	Teamwork	100	1.49	.66	3 rd
3	Effective Communication	100	1.54	.55	1 st

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

The result from table 1 shows that effective communication as a major mentoring strategy was ranked 1st, while modeling strategy and teamwork strategy as mentoring strategies were ranked 2nd, and 3rd respectively.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between mentoring strategies and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin Kwara State.

Table 2: Mentoring Strategies and School Effectiveness

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Cal r-value	P-value	Decision
Mentoring Strategies	100	1.43	.49	98	.521	.000	Ho Rejected
School Effectiveness	100	1.91	.77				

*Significant $P < .05$

Table 2 show the calculated r-value of .521 while p-value (0.000) is less than the significance level (0.05) for 98 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between mentoring strategies and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State is rejected. The finding reveals that there is significant relationship between mentoring strategies and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between modeling strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State.

Table 3. Modelling Strategy and School Effectiveness

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Cal r-value	P-value	Decision
Modelling Strategy	100	1.52	.70	98	.527	.001	Ho ₁ Rejected
School Effectiveness	100	1.91	.77				

*Significant $P < .05$

Table 3 shows the calculated r-value of .527 while p-value (0.001) is less than the significance level (0.05) for 98 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between modeling strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State is rejected. This implies that reveals that there is significant relationship between modeling strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teamwork strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin Eat, Kwara State.

Table 4: Teamwork Strategy and School Effectiveness

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Cal r-value	P-value	Decision
Teamwork Strategy	100	1.49	.66	98	.524	.000	Ho ₂ Rejected
School Effectiveness	100	1.91	.77				

*Significant $P < .05$

Table 4 shows the calculated r-value of .412 while p-value (0.000) is less than the significance level (0.05) for 98 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teamwork strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State is rejected. The finding reveals that there is significant relationship between teamwork strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin Kwara State.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between effective communication strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin Kwara State.

Table 5. Effective Communication Strategy and School Effectiveness

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Cal r-value	P-value	Decision
Effective Communication	100	1.54	.55	98	.526	.000	Ho ₃ Rejected
School Effectiveness	100	1.91	.77				

*Significant $P < .05$

Table 5 shows the calculated r-value of .526 while p-value (0.000) is less than the significance level (0.05) for 98 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between effective communication strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State is rejected. This means that there is significant relationship between effective communication strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The mentoring strategies used for school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State are ranked in 1st, 2nd and 3rd. Effective communication is mostly used in schools, followed by modelling strategy while teamwork is the least used.

The major finding of this study from the main hypothesis was that there was significant relationship between mentoring strategies and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State. This finding confirmed the finding of Heyns (2000) who opined that mentoring aims at the speedy integration and optimal utilization of every newly appointed teacher. It has long been known that the quality of teaching directly affects student learning and achievement. Darling-Hammond (2001) opined that beginning teachers who have access to intensive mentoring as a strategy not only stay in the profession at higher rates but becomes competent more quickly than those not exposed to mentoring process. The findings from hypothesis two revealed that there was significant relationship between modelling strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State. This is to say that the more the teacher demonstrate a new concept the more the students learn by observing. This correlates the works of Bandura (1986) who posited that modeling is one of the most efficient modes of learning any new skill or knowledge.

The finding from operational hypothesis 2 (Ho₂) which shows that, there is significant relationship between teamwork strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State. This finding is in line with that of Conley (2014) who observed that teamwork forming varies by its purpose such as academic team, special service team, supervision team, and administrative team. Results from operational hypothesis 3 (Ho₃) gives a clear indication that, there is significant relationship between effective communication strategy and school effectiveness in secondary schools in Ilorin East, Kwara State. This finding support that of Ijaiya (2000) who elucidated that effective communication as an active process and a purposeful, shared experience involving two or more people, one sending a message through verbal (oral) or non-verbal means (for example, use of face) and the other actively receiving it.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that mentoring consists of teaching or coaching by a more experienced people or trainers at the desk or at the bench. Mentoring is a platform where line managers are closely involved in real work situation to bring reality into the classroom, to ease the transfer of learning and to make sure that those involved in the training are carefully selected, briefed, monitored and evaluated so as to ensure that they make the right contribution. The findings led to the conclusion that mentoring strategies are key instruments for the effectiveness of a school. The importance

of teamwork, communication and modelling as the types of mentoring strategies cannot be overemphasized. The teachers however may not be aware or able to implement these strategies. This is tackled by elaborating the relevance of school administration in the running of effective school. Their contribution involves creating possible means to make these strategies implemented by the teachers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

- Teachers should be trained using mentoring strategies so as to achieve school effectiveness.
- School administrators should ensure activities which will involve pairing teachers that are new in the system with experienced teachers so that they will gain new experience from the models.
- Teamwork should be encouraged by school administrators through giving of teaching and administrative assignment to teachers so that there will be *es spirit de corp* spirit among the teachers which will definitely lead to the achievement of goals.
- Effective communication should also be encouraged among the teachers and school administrators and the medium of communication should be understandable and accessible.

REFERENCES

- Amadi, C. C. & Abraham, N. M. (2021). Mentoring service and in-service training predictors of quality job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research* 9(2): 49-58.
- Akpan, J. W., Owhor, A. G. & Nsikan, E. J. (2017). Workplace mentoring strategies and sustainable commitment of university teaching hospital staff in South-South Region of Nigeria. *Global Journal of Medical Research: K Interdisciplinary*, 17 (7), 27-34.
- Ekong, E. N., & Carolyne, S. J. (2017). Impact of mentoring on nursing and midwifery educators and students: An integrative. *Texila International Journal of Nursing*, 3(2),1-14.
- Kumar, A., Singh, S. K. & Kumar, G. (2017). Effectiveness of in-house training on technical employees in Biotech industry. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 9(1), 133-125.
- Koirela, A. & Dhungana, G. (2015). Understanding technical instructor's motivational practices in vocational training center, Morang, Nepal *Journal of Training and Development*, 1(1), 33-37.
- Klinge, M. C (2015). A conceptual framework for mentoring in a learning organization. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/10.1177/104515>
- Malik, N. A.; Agunbiade, B. A. & Arikewuyo, D. S. (2019). Effects of peer mentoring strategy on students' performances in mathematics at senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Abacus Mathematics Education Series* 44(1):130-135
- Merrick, L. (2007). Mentoring: Good practice guide resource centre for women in science, engineering and technology.
- Ofofobruku, S. A., & Nwakoby, N. P. (2015). Effects of mentoring on employees' performance in selected family business in Abuja, Nigeria. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics, and Management studies*, 4(9), 29-30.
- Osemeke, M. (2020). Mentorship as a technique for training and development of competence in Nigerian organizations. *Journal of Business and Management*, 22(6), 18-29
- Odimegwa, C. G; Udemba, N. F; & Obiekwe, K. K. (2021). Strategies for mentoring new secondary school teachers for greater performance in Anambra State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies* 8(5): 109-123.
- Olu-Ajayi, F. E. (2013). Effects of mentoring on secondary school students' cognitive achievement in Biology in South-West, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Science Education* 1(1): 190-198
- Olowu, A. A. (2013). Mentoring; A key issue in human Resource Management. Ile Ife: Ife Centre for Psychological Studies Services
- Peretomode, V.F & Pkoya, P. (2019) Mentorship: A strategic technique for achieving excellence, manpower development and nation building? *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(2),17-24
- Roll-Hansen, D. (2012). In-house training in statistical organizations: Some issues to consider and suggestions for courses. Retrieved from: https://www.ssb.no/a/english/publikasjoner/pdf/doc_201231_en/doc_201231_en.pdf
- Sarip, N. A. & Dela Cruz, M. (2022). Technological Devices: Boon or Bane? *Universal Journal of Educational Research*. 1(2), 27-34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6837255>
- Siripipathanakul, S., Shakor, M. Y., Phuangsuwan, P., & Chairprakarn, S. (2023). English Language Learning Obstacles to Second Language English Learners: A Review Article. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 2(1), 67-77. www.ujer.org/vol2no1/article128
- Ukaegbu, B.C.N., Alex- Nmecha, J.C. & Horsfall, M.N. (2014). Globalization and Information retrieval: Role of Women Librarians. A Publication of Association of Women Librarians in Nigeria (AWLIN) Book of Readings. Pp.77-84.
- Undiyaundeye, F. A., & Basake, J. A. (2017). Mentoring and career development of academics in colleges of education in Cross River State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(4), 98-104